

USING SLANG AS A TOOL FOR COMMUNICATION ON THE INTERNET

Adelina Hoxhaj

Master of Science (MSc). Department of English Language and Literature. Faculty of Philology.
State University of Tetovo. North Macedonia. Republic of Kosovo

Received: 2022-04-30

Accepted: 2022-07-10

Published online: 2022-08-29

Abstract

Slang refers to terms that are frequently regarded as defying linguistic conventions. These are ironic, artistic words that assist to identify the things that are spoken in daily speech. There are numerous competing definitions of slang in use today. The definition of slang encompasses contradiction. This specifically relates to the debate over whether all non-standard vocabulary, the use of which is strictly forbidden among educated people, should be included in the concept of slang or whether only expressive, sardonic terms that are equivalent literary words should be included. This paper looks at slang as a communication tool on the Internet, where its use is very common.

Keywords: slang, language, Internet, social networks, media.

INTRODUCTION

The exact date that the term '*slang*' first entered English oral speech is unknown. However, it is known that the word '*insulting*' was first used in literature in the 18th century. Later, this phrase took on a broader connotation and started to be used to refer to illicit simplistic words.

E. Partridge (2015) outlines various categories of unique slang among English researchers: Cockney slang, public-house slang, workers' and tradesmen's slang, slang soldiers, slang-idish (Yiddish), Kent (cant), etc. It also highlights peculiar slang expressions (oddities): Swift, medium, and gibberish slang, as well as rhymes, fractions, and swift.

R. Spears provided the definition of slang that was the most thorough (1989). He points out that the word '*slang*,' which is a synonym for the word '*kant*' was first used to describe British crime jargon. The term's definition changes through time and now encompasses a variety of non-literal vocabulary, such as jargon, duffels, dialects, and filthy words.

Thus, despite its widespread use, the term 'slang' is not terminologically accurate. Internet lingo can be categorized in various ways. Think about a few of them. Gorshkov (2007) suggested the categorization shown below: Complete borrowing, foundational borrowing, and translation, particular use of standard language, use of the lingo of other professional groups, and phonetic mimicry are all examples of plagiarism.

Additionally, we can categorize Internet slang into a number of thematic groups based on the context in which it is used, including: designation of people (guys, gf, mom); designation of human qualities (especially negative), (mummy's boy); designation of objects, places, or other objects (EBooks, ICQ, FAQ); taking any action (I want to ask u a qstn); situation assessment (ASAP, I dunno, cool); and (wow, woo, LOL, OMG).

Online expressions can also be categorized based on how they are formed:

- abbreviations (names or designations made out of a phrase's first letters);
- substituting words with symbols that have a comparable meaning (designating items in written speech with numbers and other symbols that correspond to how these objects sound when spoken);
- abbreviations (the usage of a term in a shortened form);
- words created using a reduction technique (description of the word, coinciding with its sound, contrary to grammatical rules).

INTERNET COMMUNICATION

Modern linguistics uses the term "Internet communication," which has several facets and varies in its specificity. It results from individuals maintaining an open line of communication and expressing their own opinions, future plans, and knowledge through Internet interactions, in-person meetings, and involvement in conversations with industry experts.

Web-based communication is now an essential component of modern man's social interactions. In order to transmit, exchange, or obtain information needed for shared activities like message transmission, statement linguistic design, and mutual understanding of the communicants, communication is a process of interaction between linguistic persons.

The following characteristics define internet communication as a new form of communication: an infinite number of users, anonymity, spontaneity, which mimics oral conversation, emotional communication, specific etiquette, the ability for the individual to express themselves and come into their own, etc.

Although the concepts of 'talk vocabulary,' 'slang,' 'expressiveness,' and 'emotionality,' which are specific to communication on social networks, are largely contradictory, it is undeniable that expressively evaluative and emotionally-estimated vocabulary, which is primarily used in Internet communication, is the essence of candid conversation. The desire to communicate one's own opinions and the ability of English native speakers to use their imagination as metaphorically as possible define expressivity and emotionality.

DESCRIBING POPULAR SOCIAL NETWORKS

You may have a hard time imagining the modern world without social media. This is essentially the most widely used method for both receiving and sharing information. The presence of social networks in our life today is so pervasive that practically everyone has an online "page."

A social network is primarily a website designed with the purpose of bringing together or introducing people with shared interests, exchanging information (including text, photo, video, and audio), allowing users to mark locations, and adding friends and categorizing them according to their relationships: best friends, family, coworkers, etc. Long before the Internet even existed, in 1954, the phrase "social network" was first used. American sociologist James Barnes first proposed the idea of social networks, which he defined as a person's broad interactions with other people.

With the development of the Network itself came the ability to create and maintain a variety of social connections on the Internet, including chats, teleconferences, opportunities for interactive contact, and email. All of these communication tools were initially designed more for problem-solving than for actual communication. However, the Internet's social and entertainment features quickly became one of its primary functions.

Randy Conrad founded Classmates, the first social network, in 1995. This social network was created with the intention of assisting registered members in locating and keeping in touch with friends and acquaintances they had interacted with throughout their lives, whether it be in kindergarten, elementary school, high school, college, the workplace, or the military.

Classmates.com had more than 40 million active users from the United States and Canada in 2008.

Social networks like MySpace, LinkedIn, and finally Facebook were introduced almost soon after the introduction of Classmates, which signaled the beginning of a huge enthusiasm for social networks. There are a ton of social networks available today. The most well-known of them are: *Facebook, Instagram, Tumblr, Twitter, Pinterest*, etc., with daily increases in user numbers. While attending Harvard

University, Mark Zuckerberg and his roommates established the social network 'Facebook' in 2004. The Facebook was a website that was first solely accessible to students at Harvard University. Later, registration became open to students at other Boston universities and eventually to students at any US educational institution with an email address ending in the .edu domain. All Internet users over the age of 16 with an email account have had access to the site since September 2006. There are 90 languages accessible for the social network interface.

Users of *Facebook* have access to the following opportunities: building a profile with information about themselves, generating and sharing content, controlling access, communicating with other users both publicly and privately (via personal messages), as well as through communities.

Under previously published content, users can post comments. To your communications, you can include images, videos, and locations.

Most nations recognize the social network YouTube as the largest video hosting site, offering users a variety of options for downloading and streaming video content. The business was founded on February 14, 2005, in California, United States. This initiative has established a community, become a great platform for communication and amusement, and both.

The YouTube website has grown to be the second-most visited website in the world as a result of its ease of use and accessibility. 4 billion views per day are possible. The portal offers slide displays, amateur video recordings, movies, music videos, news, and instructional activities. You need to register, create a user name, and a password in order to access this network. Additionally, registration enables you to set up your own channel. The ability to view, add, comment on, and delete videos is part of the user's administrative law rights in regard to his channel. Thus, communication—one of the key components of any social network—is accomplished.

SMARTPHONES – THE WORLD IN YOUR POCKET

Many young people already use Smartphones on a regular basis. Young and networked - Youngsters and Young People in the Digital Society, a research by the industry group BITKOM (2020), found that 84% of children between the ages of twelve and thirteen use Smartphones and other comparable devices. For children and young people to access the Internet, a Smartphone is crucial. Nearly 90% of teenagers between the ages of 16 and 18 use it online.

For many young people, a world without cellphones and the internet is inconceivable. Social networks particularly draw them in. But why are mobile gadgets and social media so crucial today? Many young people use social media to speak with their friends, play online games, and get information, according to a survey by the

website 'Ins-Netz-gehen.de.' They may now express their curiosity more quickly and easily than ever thanks to Smartphones. You may quickly access it at any moment and utilize any social media, regardless of where you are or how busy you are. Each of us may use social media to connect with individuals we know, as well as people we don't truly know, publish images and videos to the internet, post and share interesting articles, exchange ideas and information, and display ourselves to others.

For many people, having this conversation has become a crucial and daily activity. Social media also gives users the chance to communicate with others who reside far away or even in other countries. You don't lose any money due to travel or expenses, and it is time independent.

The World Wide Web can also be used to research topics or find information. Students and students who require material for their assignments, presentations, or to broaden their knowledge would particularly appreciate this. Every user starts with a search engine like 'Google,' which is remarkably quick to find the information we need.

Additionally, a wide variety of free games and applications that are created in this manner and are specifically made for Smartphones and tablets are accessible online. Even your friends can use them as suggestions.

THE NEW STANDARD

Social media has a range of opportunities for businesses as well as for kids and teenagers. The internet and social media are already on the verge of replacing traditional educational options. As previously mentioned, the Internet and numerous search engines make it easy to learn new things and look for information. Internet users now have the means to obtain what they're seeking for extremely swiftly and effortlessly thanks to the well-known search engine made available by Google. More than 80% of adolescents between the ages of 16 and 18 use the Internet to research information for school. A research conducted by the business association Bitkom supported this.

We now establish relationships through the Internet. We keep in touch with loved ones by quickly typing messages on our phones with our thumbs.

With her new book, *Because Internet: Understanding the New Rules of Language*, etymologist Gretchen McCulloch hopes to set some things straight. She claims that the 'new' rules are 'forming.'

"The new criteria center on this question: How will others interpret your speech pattern? The old rules were related to using language to demonstrate intellectual dominance, whereas the new rules were related to using language to create connections between people."

There are differences in how young people utilize 'Haha,' the acronym that originally meant 'laughing uncontrollably.' And assuming you speak with people in that age group who, as we all know, spend a lot of time online, they interpret it as follows: OK, here's an acronym; they're told it's an acronym; it should stand for 'laughing uncontrollably.' They actually utilize it as real giggling as a result. However, as time goes on, when you talk to young people, LOL could have first meant laughing, but that laughter quickly turned into positivity, as in, 'Goodness, that is kind of intriguing.' Then it stopped being genuine giggling altogether at that point. It actually meant more along the lines of 'I'm not mad at you,' 'I'm not feeling hostile,' and other obvious social overtones.

CONCLUSION

There has been debate over whether using social media negatively affects people for a number of years, especially for kids and teenagers. The subject is more prevalent than ever as current and future generations grow up and become more accustomed to technology and digital media. For today's young, using the Internet and social media is just part of daily life. We have access to new opportunities and threats through such medium.

Furthermore, LOL no longer holds any real significance for the majority of young people. It is filler that blatantly shows that there is some sort of two-sided connotation there. If I say something that can be interpreted as impolite or unpleasant, such as, 'Gracious, I scorn you,' it's okay because I'm joking when I say 'I disdain you LOL.' Instead of twisting my message and stating 'I disdain you LOL [but I'm not kidding about it],' I'm laughing wildly as I disdain you.

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